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WorldFAIR Milestone 10. WorldFAIR Findings workshop

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Introduction

The stated aim of this Milestone is to provide evidence of a workshop arranged to define overarching findings with case study participants at International Data Week 2023 (IDW2023), 23-26 October 2023, in Salzburg, Austria. However, earlier in October 2023, WorldFAIR WP02 also ran a week-long workshop, ‘Defining a Core Metadata Framework for Cross-Domain Data Sharing and Reuse’¹ on 1-6 October at Schloss Dagstuhl — the Leibniz Center for Informatics near Wadern, Germany. These two workshops were arranged to encourage case study work package participants to contribute in a practical way to the development of recommendations towards the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF), the major output of WorldFAIR Work Package 02.

This Milestone will, accordingly, outline the key points of both of these events and direct the reader to further information on each. A final section summarises the result of these activities, and describes how they will impact the development of the CDIF guidelines.

Workshop at Schloss Dagstuhl – the Leibniz Center for Informatics

The October 2023 Dagstuhl workshop included a broad range of experts from the DDI community, the WorldFAIR project — including members of the many case studies as well as the core technical working group looking at the CDIF guidelines — and representatives from other major FAIR initiatives, including various EOSC² related activities and the FAIR-IMPACT³ project.

The workshop’s goal was to identify which aspects of cross-domain FAIR can be suggested for broad reuse across domain and infrastructure boundaries at a specific level (that is, what profiles of which standards can be used for specific purposes) as well as determining which steps could be taken towards further alignment between major initiatives looking at their specific approaches to cross-domain integration and reuse.

While several different standards and models were important, the use of DDI-CDI⁴ as a generic description of data structures and resources is at the heart of this approach. No other standard for structural metadata covers the needed ground, acting as a ‘glue’ between many of the other FAIR standards and models. As a further outcome of this work, CDIF may also drive significant uptake of the nascent DDI-CDI standard.

¹ [https://ddi-alliance.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/DDI4/pages/2946531350/2023+Defining+a+Core+Metadata+Framework+for+Cross-Domain+Data+Sharing+and+Reuse#Workshop-Schedule-\(TBD\)](https://ddi-alliance.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/DDI4/pages/2946531350/2023+Defining+a+Core+Metadata+Framework+for+Cross-Domain+Data+Sharing+and+Reuse#Workshop-Schedule-(TBD)). It should be noted that the series of DDI Workshops at Schloss Dagstuhl is a long-standing activity. CODATA has been collaborating on these, precisely in relation to DDI-CDI and cross-domain interoperability challenges, since 2018. WorldFAIR partners and WPs have been strongly involved in the 2022 and 2023 editions. We have ensured that each of the WorldFAIR Case Studies has been represented at least once across the 2022 and 2023 Dagstuhl workshops.

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

³ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

⁴ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi>

Preparation for the workshop

In order to ensure a productive workshop, WorldFAIR participants were supplied with rich introductory and support materials about the CDIF, prior to the event. These were:

- Video of presentation from the Dagstuhl briefing session in September 2023⁵
- CDIF progress report⁶
- CDIF GitHub repo⁷
- CDIF Discoverability Draft⁸
- CDIF Design Principles Draft⁹
- Recording from the CDIF webinar in June 2023¹⁰
- Presentations from the CDIF webinar in June 2023¹¹

Structure of the workshop

At this workshop, we arranged four topic-based groups to encourage focused discussion. These topics were:

a) Discovery and Access

This group looked at existing work regarding data discovery and access, and extended this to address the related aspects of data assessment and evaluation. While there are several discrete areas involved in these functions, much of the metadata required is the same. This group considered these functions and how they combine, with an eye toward defining a coherent set of metadata appropriate to each distinct step, up to the point of integration and analysis.

After initial discussion, this group divided into two sub-groups, ‘Discovery’ and ‘Access’.

The Access subgroup worked on identifying several scenarios in which standard information about the access conditions of digital resources could be expressed in a way which enables greater automated support for determining and negotiating access (in those cases where it is required). Recommendations for how the metadata to support the more-immediate use cases were drafted, as a working input to the CDIF recommendations. More complex scenarios are provided as a roadmap for further work, and as the basis of prototyping efforts.

⁵ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/13lcctu2iKAmnuzoA8OH3kHU5eoacaZ5e/view?usp=sharing>

⁶ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1dlGnxiSvvtCkxOAp1LEDNficxCNnXBZZ/view?usp=sharing>

⁷ <https://github.com/Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework>

⁸ <https://github.com/Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework/Discovery/blob/main/discoverability.md>

⁹ <https://github.com/Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework/principles/blob/main/Design%20principles-Draft.md>

¹⁰

<https://worldfair-project.eu/event/worldfair-deliverable-webinar-series-fair-implementation-profiles-the-cross-domain-interopability-framework-and-the-worldfair-methodology/>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099435>

The Discovery group worked from an existing draft of recommendations for how basic discovery metadata can be encoded in a standard fashion, based on Schema.org. This group looked at how the description of data could be extended to the variable level. Several different models were compared, including Schema.org, DCAT, and DDI-CDI. This group also looked at how these data descriptions could be used as the basis for a system for determining conformance to these (and other) CDIF profiles, using a SHACL-based description of the profiles. It also addressed the connection between the objects described for Access, by that sub-group, and the way in which data is exposed for use (as DCAT Distributions).

b) Integration and Semantic Mapping

Data integration has several aspects, among which are the combination of data at a structural level, and the ability to equate similar semantics related to the data. The roles played by concepts are the point of contact between these. While structural manipulation of data can be automated to a great extent, the mapping of semantics — even when informed by knowledge of the roles played by the relevant concepts — is much less prone to automation. This group looked at how the different aspects of data integration can be addressed, and what is possible or desirable in terms of automation and support for non-automated activities.

c) Standard Expression of “Universals”

Some types of information do not require domain-specific expression, either because they are described in a consistent fashion across domain boundaries, or because the domain descriptions of them are universally employed. This category includes not only time, geography, and (basic) units of measure, but also extends to such ubiquitous classifications as the species taxonomy.

Understanding where a ‘lingua franca’ such as CDIF is needed, and where it is not, is important in providing guidance to adopters. This group will explore where these limitations are, and the implications for interoperability across domain boundaries.

The group outlined and began drafting guidelines around how time and geography should be addressed, and explored the idea of domain-specific universals based on how chemicals can be identified.

d) Events, Occurrences, and Samples

Many domains have similar approaches for organising their data: events become the subject of measurements. Often, samples are a critical aspect of such approaches. The act of measurement is often an important focus. Measurements of specific objects are made for reasons that can only be understood in the context of what is being studied, but often the description of such subjects is implicit in publications or other uses of the data, rather than being an explicit part of the metadata. When included, it is often under-specified for cross-domain use of the data, based on the implicit domain knowledge of its traditional users.

This type of data description — and the description of relevant data collection and sampling events, and more generally the objects of study — has implications for what constitutes sufficient

provenance information. These elements are combined in different ways across domains, and yet bear many similarities.

The goal of this group was to identify similarities across domains, and to consider the requirements for exchange of this information across domain boundaries. The discussion was an exploratory one, drawing on the models and standards which address these topics such as GBIF¹², OGC's Observations & Measurements¹³, PROV-O¹⁴, and others.

e) Editorial group

In addition, there was a transversal group for cross-cutting and presentational/editorial issues. The organisation and presentation of the CDIF guidelines requires that each functional area be presented in a stepwise fashion, with a clear return on effort for adoption. If CDIF is to be adopted by the target communities, it must be easy to understand what should be implemented by practitioners in different domains, according to what data they wish to provide for cross-domain use. This group looks at any such cross-cutting issues and how they can be addressed and documented for the purposes of the CDIF guidelines. It performed a coordinating role across the work of other groups, as needed, and will carry forward the work on the editing of group outputs as they continue to emerge post-workshop.

Workshop at IDW 2023

At International Data Week 2023, we held a session on WorldFAIR and the emerging CDIF proposals. This is described in detail at <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2023-Salzburg/sessions/555/>. In addition to the presenters listed on the session description, Yann Le Franc provided a summary of data integration discussions at Dagstuhl, and Darren Bell set out the progress on discussions on discovery and access. A video recording of this session is available from the SciDataCon Vimeo collection¹⁵ and will be embedded in the WorldFAIR website.

Prior to this session, a workshop was held to review the outputs from the earlier Dagstuhl workshop (the “Events, Occurrences, and Samples” topic) and to discuss these further with the WorldFAIR case studies. In particular, these centred around the ‘variable’ cascade and the ‘unit’ cascade. Representatives of WorldFAIR case study work packages were invited to participate in this meeting, either in person or online. Eleven people attended, representing WPs 01 (Project Management), 02 (Synthesis and Coordination), 03 (Chemistry), 04 (Nanomaterials), 05 (Geochemistry), 07 (Population Health), 10 (Agricultural Biodiversity — Pollination), 13 (Cultural Heritage) and 14 (Communications and Outreach), and meeting notes are shared with all project members.

Between the work at Schloss Dagstuhl and in this workshop, a methodology for use across domains

¹² <https://www.gbif.org/>

¹³ <https://www.ogc.org/standard/om/>

¹⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹⁵ <https://vimeo.com/877736268/9d10124da9>

has emerged. This has two significant parts: data context, and connection of that context to the structural data description. Context includes identification of the process and design aspects of any given data set - how was it produced, and what was it designed to measure? What were the significant resources and actors? The methodology drew on a technique employed by GBIF (the lead of WorldFAIR WP09) to understand the processes, provenance and data coming from the increasing number of ‘sub-domains’ in biodiversity. The modelling is done using adapted forms of the W3C PROV-O model, the OGC Observations & Measurements model, and the W3C SOSA-SSN ontology¹⁶.

These aspects are then associated with the detailed description of the structure of the data. The IDW Workshop focused on this second question, to answer the questions “What is this data?” and “What is this data *about*?” The DDI-CDI specification offers a core model for answering these questions in a standard, machine-actionable way, and suggests how the two sides of this analysis can be connected. Together, they provide a useful way of understanding the fundamentals of data across domains, covering samples and events as the subject of measurement and observation, and how these can be described for sufficient navigation by computers.

DDI Cross-Domain Integration Model of the “Cascades”

¹⁶ W3C PROV-O: The PROV Ontology <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-o-20130430/>; OGC OM <https://www.ogc.org/standard/om/>; W3C SSN (Semantic Sensor Network Ontology) <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>

Analysis and summary

These activities were prompted by the need to identify commonalities to address some of the questions which arise when data and metadata is exchanged across domain boundaries, stemming from the implicit understanding of the data within a domain or discipline which is often unknown in other domains or disciplines. Among these are questions regarding the specifics of what data is and how and why it was collected. In order to use data coming from across domain boundaries, it must be discoverable and understandable, a process which involves making the answers to such questions explicit.

Such a description of the object of study and the purpose of the data collection can only be answered if there is a shared conceptual frame which is meaningful across domain boundaries. The meetings described above were intended to explore what this frame of reference might look like, by examining how such questions are answered within existing domains that are themselves very broad in scope. If a methodology can be developed for formalising descriptions across domain boundaries, then it must be applicable broadly, in domains which are smaller or more focused. The method described here was also explored.

In the Dagstuhl event, the outline of such a framework and methodology emerged: by analysing the process of data collection, and understanding what the object of study is, and how it is measured, repeatedly across disparate domains, it became clear that events and samples were significant candidates as the “units of study” alongside more obvious topics such as particular species, humans, households, etc.

The process-based analysis showed how such units of study interact with the activity of observation and measurement, and the shape of an appropriate methodology based on the PROV-O standard emerged. The second workshop explored how such an analysis can be applied to the data itself, which is the end product of the observation/measurement process, but serves as the reused object in cross-domain research.

The unit of study can be described at different levels (the “unit cascade”) and this can be reflected meaningfully in the metadata describing that data at different levels of specificity (the “variable cascade”). Such a description refines the existing “feature of interest” (and similar, insufficiently specific) into something more useful, and capable of supporting search and reuse at all needed levels for the purposes of WorldFAIR (that is, discovery, assessment, and integration/reuse of data).

This exploration is far from complete, but a useful methodology for approaching domains, and specifying the needed information to describe the subject and context of data in an explicit fashion has emerged. The further development of this approach is expected as the project proceeds, resulting in a set of recommended fields within the CDIF metadata framework, and a systematic approach to populating the needed metadata consistently across domains. This methodology could be employed alongside the use of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)¹⁷ and other efforts as a way of realising more detailed formal descriptions of FAIR data in cross-domain scenarios.

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/7378109>

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In sum, the Dagstuhl Workshop, the WorldFAIR IDW side workshop to review the Dagstuhl discussions and the IDW-SciDataCon session certainly enabled us to define the overarching findings from the case study work packages in relation to the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework and other aspects of the WorldFAIR activities.

